

RETHINKING DATA PRACTICES FOR ECOLOGICAL FUTURES: TOMATOES AS EMBODIED DATA

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ABSTRACT

Notions of data are increasingly tied to digital databases and underlying technologies, which often translate reality into immaterial, fixed, and independent forms of representation and create untenable promises for endless economic growth in a finite material world. In my PhD, I argue that such notions can be problematic as they limit our ability to retain an entangled reality that extends beyond anthropocentrism and impacts the more-than-human world. My practice-based research with fictional artifacts and participatory workshops uses tomatoes to explore the potential of living organisms as alternative data embodying material and relational aspects of the world. This is a provocation to reconsider our current notions of data and acknowledge that data consists of various heterogeneous sources, relationships, and contexts. Such sources include not only humans and machines but also plants, animals, and minerals. This expanded understanding of the world can help us pay attention to responsibility, care, and appreciation.

INTRODUCTION

Today, we rely on representational and computational words, numbers, and visuals to interpret, demarcate, control, and predict the world (Deleuze, G., & Guattari, 1988; Borgmann, 1999; Barad, 2003). This tendency is often linked to databases, which have become fundamental to our socio-economic systems (McQuillan, 2018). With profit-driven attention and power, we have sought to diminish the unknown and complicated aspects of nature, translating it into controllable, measurable, and predictable ones through a human exceptionalism approach (Crawford, 2013; Haraway, 2016; Heitlinger et al., 2021).

Furthermore, living entities, such as tomatoes, have become engineerable and predictable resources, commodities, and models for digital twins through technology. This technology enables us to believe that we can create an inevitable fate for them, as if we were gods. In the process, countless quantifiable data have been generated to grow tomato plants, create controllable environments, and transport them without harm, in order to sell them as perfect-looking products in a supermarket.

As we generate increasingly vast amounts of data and information produced from tomatoes, however, this somehow obscures our ability to evoke emotions, memories, experiences, and stories about tomato seeds, plants, as well as fruits. When you see data from a package and food label of tomatoes, can you imagine what the environment looks like where tomatoes grow? In your imagination, where do you place the soil, animals, plants, humans, and machines? What if we reconsider data by using the material body and agency (Bennett, 2010) of tomatoes as a lens?

This work aims to problematise the limitations and challenges of current notions of data and propose a new way of reconsidering data onto-epistemologically and revealing the potential of materiality and relationality of data through design practice (Lupton, 2018; D’Ignazio & Klein, 2020; Lee et al., 2022). This work will allow designers and non-designers to raise critical questions about current notions of data, explore new mindsets and practices in a tangible way with an ordinary organism and applicable context and envision ecological futures. Ultimately, my goal is to answer the question: “How can design provoke a new approach to data and encourage experts in an economic system to reconsider their data and data practice towards an ecological and more-than-human world?”

Figure 1. Discussion about data from a pack of tomatoes in a workshop.

Figure 2. Discussion about feelings, memories and experiences associated with tomatoes in a workshop.

METHOD

Through participatory and speculative methods, I utilize tomatoes as a provocation to 1) rethink and extend our notions of data, 2) envision ecological worlds grounded in social, technological, and environmental contexts and 3) reflect on the current data and data practices with diverse experts such as farmers, gardeners, scientists, and a municipality in food systems.

To achieve this, I will start by contextualizing objectified tomatoes through a mapping exercise that

involves data, human and non-human entities, and environments (Culhane & Elliott, 2016; Springgay & Truman, 2017). This will reveal the symbolic and functional meanings of the entangled contextual relationships and recover the contingency and animacy of the tomatoes.

Next, visuals of future tomatoes and fictional stories about them will be generated through participatory workshops by imagining how social, technological, and environmental trends might impact the phenotypes of tomatoes and the relationships that emerge from the mapping exercise of the status quo (Bleecker, 2009; Coulton et al., 2017). These provocative artefacts and stories will help people reconsider data and imagine possible, yet unknown, futures from an ecological perspective.

Finally, I will collect the outcomes (future tomato artefacts and stories) of workshops and develop them as design artefacts. This will enable us to discuss and reflect on different data and data practices through provocative artefacts by engaging diverse experts such as scientists, farmers, distributors, chefs, and civil servants.

RESULTS IN PROGRESS

To date, I have established my conceptual framework for ‘data practice through design’ based on post-humanism and new materialism theories (Lee et al., 2022), and ethnographic fieldwork in urban farming. Furthermore, I have organized 2 workshops to explore the potential of the material and contextual nature of living organisms for rethinking data and promoting an ecological perception.

- Lee, Y., Pschetz, L., & Speed, C. (2022). Investigating materiality for a renewed focus on data practice through design. *DRS2022: Bilbao, 25*. This positioning paper describes the initial conceptual framework, which will be developed further.
- *Recontextualisation of objectified entities for ecological futures*. A workshop organised for MA students of Design informatics at the University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh, UK
- *Imagining the life cycle of tomatoes with diverse human and non-human purposes and contexts*. A workshop organised for Designing Temporal Ecology symposium participants at the University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh, UK

Through this work, I have learned that tomatoes, a common commodity that fits into human economic systems yet is a living organism, have the strong power to allow designers and non-designers to experience the significance of embodied data, experience, and

knowledge, creating attention to appreciation, responsibility, and care towards the natural world. Tomatoes as data, evidence and signal of the world help us to feel, question, and imagine unexpected encounters, relationships, and flows that exist beyond them, serving as an entry point to explore the unknown.

EXPECTED OUTCOMES

My expected outcomes include conceptual frameworks and a toolkit that consists of a mapping exercise for contextualising the current state of tomatoes and a speculative design exercise for creating fictional tomato phenotypes and stories with experts in the agricultural context. I hope this research will contribute to providing tangible methods and examples that can help both designers and non-designers unpack challenges and opportunities in designing or undesigning for a more-than-human world in practice.

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